

Born Rule and Many-Worlds Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics: An Ergodic Approach Towards the Ontological Aspects of the Interpretation

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Abstract: In this paper, the ontological aspects of the Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics are studied by employing measure theoretical methods of the ergodic theory. Before everything it is shown that the frequency interpretation of the Born rule is independent of the measurement postulate and hence, must be extended to the statistical ontology of the MWI. Then, based on Birkhoff's ergodic theorem we will prove that except for a Lebesgue null set of extremely rare parallel worlds, the Born rule will be refuted in all of the parallel worlds created in a long-term process of consecutive experiments in the MWI of quantum mechanics. This reduces the unlimited ontology of the MWI to an extremely confined but still uncountable set of possible parallel worlds in long-term processes and lets us acknowledge a pseudo-deterministic mechanism of quantum mechanics in the statistical picture of the theory. Hence, we conclude that the common understanding of the unconstrained MWI ontology, even if considered valid, cannot survive in long-term consecutive observations and must soon collapse into a more constrained interpretation of quantum mechanics.

Keywords: Many-Worlds Interpretation, Born Rule, Measure Theory, Lebesgue Measure, Birkhoff's Ergodic Theorem, Born-Vaidman Rule, Statistical Interpretation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Born rule or the quantum probability is one of the most controversial topics in the Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics. In principle, the Born rule is one of the most significant features of quantum mechanics which connects the theoretical contents to the empirical achievements of the theory and hence, its application in the MWI, as an untestable picture, is questioned seriously by numerous physicists.¹ However, the ambiguous and unreliable position of the Born rule in the MWI is a real criticism of the interpretation, since, in fact, the Born rule is one of the most conceptual, authentic, and pivotal postulates of quantum mechanics that was proposed by delicate scrutiny and profound understanding of the theory² and has been extensively accepted by numerous laboratory confirmations and a huge number of everyday experiences of natural phenomena that are related to quantum physics.³

More precisely, the MWI is actually a deterministic theory, and the concept of probability in such a theory corresponds to an ignorance of the observer. This ignorance is, in fact, due to the observer's

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¹ See for example the arguments in [3, 13, 17, 39, 47–49, 52, 55, 66, 71].

² For a brief review of the history of the Born rule see [10, 11, 22, 42, 45, 46, 58, 79].

³ See for example the discussions in [50, 77].

information before being aware of the result of the quantum measurement, and can be studied from the ontological perspective of the MWI [67, 69, 72, 74, 75]. Therefore, some physicists have tried to correspond this entirely ambiguous concept to a kind of mental activity, the continuity of mind, the decision theory, and the consciousness,⁴ while some others have speculated that to perceive the concept of probability in the MWI the ignorance must be figured out upon more basic foundations [73, 74]. Addressing the idea of ignorance some investigations have tried to explain such a concept by interpreting probability with semantic viewpoints towards diverging parallel worlds and defining a kind of weight for them [65],⁵ but there seems to be no consensus on the details of such an approach [39, 47–49, 55, 71].

In addition, explanations based on decoherence theory and unitary evolutions have also been proposed in defining the concept of probability in Everett’s interpretation of quantum mechanics [5, 37, 38, 85],⁶ but, nevertheless, the problem of probability in the MWI is still widely open [76]. In fact, the main root of the controversy of probability in the MWI stems from different understandings of the interpretation. As a thought-provoking and mesmerizing philosophical viewpoint to quantum mechanics, it is well understood that there are various explanations of the MWI [14, 15, 18, 21, 23–26, 41, 53, 54, 61, 64, 76, 88] and, hence, based on different comprehensions of the theory, variant approaches exist to the problem of probability in the interpretation [3, 12, 19, 29, 59, 75, 76, 83, 89].⁷ In this paper, we will base our study on Vaidman’s explanation of the MWI nicely proposed in [75, 76], while instead of discussing the semantic description of the Born rule in every single observation we focus on the frequency interpretation of probability and its experimental aspects in the ontology of the theory.

Based on this understanding of the MWI, although it is a deterministic theory with no objective chancy probability, the experiences in a particular parallel world are identical to the experiences of the observers living in the physical universe and approving the measurement postulate of quantum mechanics by accepting the collapses of the wave function and, hence both have the same understanding of the genuine probability. This explains the illusion of probability in Everett’s interpretation of quantum mechanics [75].⁸ The idea is best perceived via a gedanken experiment, known as *sleeping pill* [73], and is considered as a semantic/ontological presume of the MWI, the so-called *probability postulate* or the *Born-Vaidman rule*. According to the Born-Vaidman rule *the subjective probability of a particular outcome of a specific quantum measurement is in proportion to the total measure of the existence of all worlds with that outcome* [69, 76]. In fact, with the Born-Vaidman rule, the measure of existence is best understood to be inversely proportional to the number of all possible outcomes whenever all parallel worlds have the same likelihood for appearance and hence, all parallel worlds have equal measures of existence.

Nevertheless, understanding the problem of probability through the above perspective is entirely

⁴ See the discussions in [3, 4, 12, 19, 20, 83].

⁵ See also [86, 87].

⁶ See [13, 32, 56, 78, 80] for other proposals.

⁷ Indeed, this issue could also be seen in the reverse direction, that is, one may claim that each interpretation of quantum mechanics hinges on a specific interpretation of probability and has its own perception of the Born rule [51].

⁸ See [3, 59] for more discussions. However, there are more semantic/theoretical interpretations of the probability postulate in Everett’s theory. See for example [57, 62, 70, 77]. See also [19, 36, 81–84] and [89] as two alternative approaches to the problem.

conceptual rather than experimental. This means that the mentioned viewpoint and its developed formulations of the probability problem in Everett's theory are based on semantic interpretations of the relative weight of the creation of a particular parallel world at the quantum measurement. As mentioned above this weighted probability has no empirical evidence, while it seems that it is an illusion not properly describable by merely the assumptions of the MWI.⁹ On the other hand, from the viewpoint of experimentalists, the point of view which we insist on in this study, the essence of the theoretical/empirical definition of quantum probability stems from the frequency of observations in a long-term process of consecutive measurements which may or may not be described via the measurement postulate of quantum mechanics and the wave function collapse.¹⁰

Strictly speaking, in the present research, our approach is somehow different and aims to understand and figure out the concept of probability in the MWI based on its frequency explanation and statistical nature. In fact, we believe that in the MWI the only way to comprehend the concept of probability is to use its statistical meaning based on an ensemble of quantum states and a chain of consecutive quantum measurements.¹¹ In other words, instead of considering an agent who is performing a single measurement on a given quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ and asking the probability of the creation of a specified parallel world, we assume an endless ensemble of copies of $|\psi\rangle$ and consider all the parallel worlds created by performing infinite measurements and then enquire: *In how many of the created parallel worlds the agents would approve the Born rule?*

The above approach not only provides a definite empirical explanation for the theoretical meaning of probability in the deterministic Everett's interpretation of quantum mechanics but also gives rise to an ontological viewpoint of the problem of probability in the MWI and conducts some valuable assessments of it. Moreover, as we will demonstrate in the following it will shed more light on the fundamental basis of quantum physics and will show us that despite its random nature quantum mechanics admits a pseudo-deterministic law for the history of outcomes due to the Born rule. In addition, by studying the above approach we will establish that the ontology of the MWI should be revisited by concentrating on the physical reality related to the statistical history of the observations that respect the Born rule. Next, we will argue that the conclusion of our study is intimately correlated with the theoretical necessity of the symmetric probability of outcomes in the Born-Vaidman rule.

II. CONTROVERSY: EVERETT'S THEORY AND THE BORN RULE

As stated above, the credence of the Born rule in the MWI is a controversial problem. Different understandings of the issue stem from distinct explanations of the interpretation [19, 59, 75, 81, 89]. Although there have been extensive endeavors to establish or reconstruct the Born rule in the MWI as a semantic statement for each individual measurement,¹² our main question is about the validity of the frequency interpretation of the Born rule in the statistical assessment of the ontology of the

⁹ Some physicists believe that the meaning of probability in the MWI can be directly extracted from the assumptions of the interpretation via the decision theory [19, 81], while it seems that there is no consensus about this claim [75, 76].

¹⁰ In fact, the pragmatic attitude of most physicists about probability is defined by the frequency interpretation of what is experienced in the laboratory [28, 34].

¹¹ See [35] for its similar viewpoint.

¹² See for example [76, 77] and the references therein.

interpretation. We will show that a scrutiny of the empirical aspects of the MWI and establishing a statistical insight into the ontological features of the interpretation can disclose an extensive amount of information about the reliability of Everett's theory and the limits of its validity.

Therefore, it may be questioned if the Born rule is statistically admitted in the MWI or if it must be discarded from the statistical picture of the interpretation. In fact, we have to figure out whether the statistical interpretation of the Born rule is independent of the measurement postulate or it stems from the wave function collapse assumption. If we answer this question we will be able to assess the significance of the role of the Born rule in confining the unlimited ontology of the MWI to more specific possibilities.¹³ Here, throughout the next theorem, we will try to provide a concise answer to the question by the minimal usage of the principles of quantum mechanics and based on the frequency interpretation of quantum probability in the classical limits. As we will see in the following, this will help us to have a more concrete discussion about the ontology of the MWI.

Theorem 1; *The statistical interpretation of the Born rule can be derived from the other principles of quantum mechanics in the classical limits.¹⁴ In addition, the frequency interpretation of the Born rule is theoretically independent of the measurement postulate with the wave function collapse mechanism.*

Proof;¹⁵ For simplicity, we provide the proof for an experiment with a finite number n ($n \geq 2$) of possible outcomes without degeneracy. The extension to the general case would be immediate. Let

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha_0|0\rangle + \cdots + \alpha_{n-1}|n-1\rangle \quad (\text{II.1})$$

be a general quantum state with $\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} |\alpha_k|^2 = 1$, while $|i\rangle$ s are the orthonormal eigenstates of the operator \hat{O} with eigenvalues λ_{i} s ($0 \leq i \leq n-1$). Assume that there are prepared a large number N of $|\psi\rangle$ and set

$$\hat{O}_k = 1 \otimes \cdots \otimes \underbrace{\hat{O}}_{k\text{-th}} \otimes \cdots \otimes 1 \quad \text{and} \quad |\psi\rangle_k = 1 \otimes \cdots \otimes \underbrace{|\psi\rangle}_{k\text{-th}} \otimes \cdots \otimes 1 \quad (\text{II.2})$$

respectively as the tensor product operator and the tensor product state in the Fock space with total N components.¹⁶

¹³ Meanwhile, there have been some successful attempts to derive the Born rule from the other fundamentals of quantum mechanics. Such derivations of the Born rule have extensively been accepted in the literature [1, 2, 27, 40, 50, 78]. Although the strategies of the proofs have been questioned or criticized by some other authors [13, 30, 68, 77].

¹⁴ We should note that the Born rule is sometimes put out of the principles of quantum mechanics in the literature. See [77] for more details.

¹⁵ The proof is, in fact, mostly based on the discussions in [2], however, it not only avoids the use of the "pointer state" but also includes new equations that are derived based on statistical interpretations and shows different aspects of the discussion.

¹⁶ Each vector $|\psi\rangle$ in (II.2) is, in fact, not considered as an element of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} , but rather as an element of the Fock space \mathcal{F} , which is a generalization of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} generated by its elements as: $\mathcal{F} = \mathbb{C} \oplus \mathcal{H} \oplus \mathcal{H}^{2\odot} \oplus \mathcal{H}^{3\odot} \oplus \cdots$, where $\mathcal{H}^{k\odot} = \mathcal{H} \odot \cdots \odot \mathcal{H}$ (k times). We note that here, \odot must be replaced by the symmetric tensor product \vee for bosons and the anti-symmetric tensor product (wedge product) \wedge for fermions. Indeed, \mathcal{F} is both a Hilbert space and an associative algebra with unity $1 \in \mathbb{C}$. With this unit structure, we have $1 \odot |f\rangle = |f\rangle \odot 1 = |f\rangle$, for all $|f\rangle \in \mathcal{F}$. In this regard, the tensor product \otimes in the second equation of (II.2) is used between the copies of \mathcal{F} . Hence, $|\psi\rangle_k = 1 \otimes \cdots \otimes |\psi\rangle(k\text{-th}) \otimes \cdots \otimes 1$ belongs to $\mathcal{F}^{N\otimes} = \mathcal{F} \otimes \cdots \otimes \mathcal{F}$ (N times).

Define the average operator $\overline{\mathcal{O}}$ and the ensemble state $\overline{|\psi\rangle}$ as¹⁷

$$\overline{\mathcal{O}} = \frac{1}{N} \left(\oplus_{k=1}^N \hat{\mathcal{O}}_k \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{|\psi\rangle} = \prod_{k=1}^N |\psi\rangle_k = \underbrace{|\psi\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |\psi\rangle}_{N \text{ copies}}. \quad (\text{II.3})$$

Since we readily find

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle = \langle\psi|\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle|\psi\rangle + \varepsilon_{\hat{\mathcal{O}}}|\psi_{\perp}\rangle, \quad (\text{II.4})$$

for some vertical state $|\psi_{\perp}\rangle$ (i.e. $\langle\psi|\psi_{\perp}\rangle = 0$ and $|\psi_{\perp}\rangle = 1$), and some $\varepsilon_{\hat{\mathcal{O}}} \in \mathbb{C}$. Indeed, $\varepsilon_{\hat{\mathcal{O}}}$ depends on $|\psi\rangle$ and the matrix structure of $\hat{\mathcal{O}}$ such as its eigenvalues λ_i s and their corresponding eigenspaces.¹⁸ Anyway, one can easily compute:

$$\overline{\mathcal{O}}\overline{|\psi\rangle} = \langle\psi|\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle\overline{|\psi\rangle} + \frac{\varepsilon_{\hat{\mathcal{O}}}}{N} \oplus_{k=1}^N \left(\left(\prod_{l=1, l \neq k}^N |\psi\rangle_l \right) |\psi_{\perp}\rangle_k \right). \quad (\text{II.5})$$

The latter term in (II.5) has the norm of $\varepsilon_{\hat{\mathcal{O}}}/\sqrt{N}$ and disappears as $N \rightarrow \infty$. In this limit the ensemble state $\overline{|\psi\rangle}$ turns into the eigenstate of the average operator $\overline{\mathcal{O}}$ with the eigenvalue $\langle\psi|\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle$, i.e.;

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \overline{\mathcal{O}}\overline{|\psi\rangle} = \langle\psi|\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle\overline{|\psi\rangle}. \quad (\text{II.6})$$

On the other hand, (II.6) can be interpreted via statistical concepts. To see this, one should note that $\overline{|\psi\rangle}$ is naturally decomposed into the eigenvectors of $\overline{\mathcal{O}}$ for any N . In principle, we have

$$\overline{|\psi\rangle} = \sum_{i_1, \dots, i_N \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}} \kappa_{i_1 \dots i_N} |i_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |i_N\rangle, \quad (\text{II.7})$$

where $\kappa_{i_1 \dots i_N}$ s are the corresponding expansion coefficients. Now, let us define

$$|N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}\rangle := \sum_{\text{components including } N_i \text{ copies of } |i\rangle \ (i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\})} \kappa_{i_1 \dots i_N} |i_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |i_N\rangle. \quad (\text{II.8})$$

Hence, we read:

$$\overline{|\psi\rangle} = \sum_{N_0 + \dots + N_{n-1} = N} |N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}\rangle. \quad (\text{II.9})$$

Obviously, $|N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}\rangle$ is an eigenvector of $\overline{\mathcal{O}}$ with eigenvalue

$$\Lambda_{N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \lambda_i \frac{N_i}{N}. \quad (\text{II.10})$$

¹⁷ The product of two elements of $\mathcal{F}^{N \otimes}$ is defined in the standard way;

$(|f_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |f_N\rangle) \odot (|f'_1\rangle \otimes \cdots \otimes |f'_N\rangle) = (|f_1\rangle \odot |f'_1\rangle) \otimes \cdots \otimes (|f_N\rangle \odot |f'_N\rangle) \in \mathcal{F}^{N \otimes}$.

¹⁸ Using the Gram-Schmidt theorem we can define an orthonormal basis for the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} including $|\psi\rangle$ as $\{|e_1\rangle = |\psi\rangle, |e_2\rangle, \dots, |e_n\rangle\}$, with $\langle e_i | e_j \rangle = \delta_{ij}$. Now, we readily find $\mathbf{1} = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| + \sum_{i=2}^n |e_i\rangle\langle e_i|$, and hence, $\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle = \mathbf{1}\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle = \langle\psi|\hat{\mathcal{O}}|\psi\rangle|\psi\rangle + \sum_{i=2}^n b_i |e_i\rangle$, where $b_i = \langle e_i | \hat{\mathcal{O}} | \psi \rangle$ depends on both $|\psi\rangle$ and the structure of $\hat{\mathcal{O}}$. Obviously, $|\phi_{\perp}\rangle := \varepsilon_{\hat{\mathcal{O}}} |\psi_{\perp}\rangle := \sum_{i=2}^n b_i |e_i\rangle$ is perpendicular to $|e_1\rangle = |\psi\rangle$, while its norm is: $\varepsilon_{\hat{\mathcal{O}}} = \sqrt{\langle \phi_{\perp} | \phi_{\perp} \rangle} = \sqrt{b_2^2 + \cdots + b_n^2}$.

For general eigenvalues λ_i s, as we consider here, the degeneracy $D_{\Lambda_{N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}}}$ of $\Lambda_{N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}}$ is

$$D_{\Lambda_{N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}}} = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \binom{N - \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} N_j}{N_i} = \binom{N}{N_0} \times \binom{N - N_0}{N_1} \times \dots \times \binom{N_{n-2} + N_{n-1}}{N_{n-2}}. \quad (\text{II.11})$$

Since the eigenspaces of these eigenvalues are orthogonal to each other, then according to (II.6), as $N \rightarrow \infty$ the ensemble state $|\overline{\psi}\rangle$ must be confined to the eigenspace of a unique $\Lambda_{N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}}$. In this regard, based on (II.6) we obtain

$$\Lambda_{N_0, \dots, N_{n-1}} = \langle \psi | \hat{\mathcal{O}} | \psi \rangle \quad (\text{II.12})$$

whenever $N \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, according to (II.10) we find

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \lambda_i \frac{N_i}{N} = \langle \psi | \hat{\mathcal{O}} | \psi \rangle, \quad (\text{II.13})$$

which is, in fact, the statistical description of the Born rule. Now, on the one hand, we have

$$\langle \psi | \hat{\mathcal{O}} | \psi \rangle = \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_i |\alpha_i|^2, \quad (\text{II.14})$$

from the linear algebra, while on the other hand, we have to compute $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \lambda_i \frac{N_i}{N}$. Hence;¹⁹

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_i \frac{N_i}{N} = \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda_i |\alpha_i|^2. \quad (\text{II.15})$$

Therefore, since α_i s are arbitrary we conclude that

$$|\alpha_i|^2 = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_i}{N}. \quad (\text{II.16})$$

This proves the first claim of the theorem. On the other hand, to extract the equality of (II.16) no use has been made of the wave function collapse mechanism. This shows that the frequency interpretation of the Born rule is independent of the measurement postulate. Therefore, the theorem follows. **Q.E.D.**

According to **Theorem 1**, the measurement postulate or the wave function collapse assumption has no relevant contribution to the derivation of the Born rule in the statistical interpretations of quantum mechanics. In other words, the collapse assumption has no role in deriving the critical equations of the proof of **Theorem 1**; i.e., (II.10), (II.13), and (II.14). All these equations are derived from either the underlying linear algebra of quantum mechanics or from the statistical features of the ensemble. That is, the Born rule must be considered in the ontological aspects of all the interpretations that admit the basic principles of the theory but may refute the axiom of the wave function collapse. Hence, from the contents of **Theorem 1** we conclude that:

¹⁹ See [2, 77] as a different derivation approach for the equation (II.14) based on the entanglement states of the quantum system and the measurement device.

Corollary 1; *The frequency interpretation of the Born rule must be imposed on the ontology of the MWI for any long-term history of consecutive measurements. In other words, the ontology of the MWI must be seriously reconsidered based on the consequences of the Born rule in statistical aspects of the interpretation.*

As we will see in the next section there is a large amount of parallel worlds whose agents disapprove of the Born rule statistically. Therefore, according to **Corollary 1** the ontology of the MWI for a long-term process of consecutive measurements must be reduced from the unlimited set of all possible parallel worlds to the set of the parallel worlds whose sentient beings confirm the Born rule statistically. However, it must be emphasized that this modification of the ontology is merely considered in long-term processes of measurements and does not affect the assumption of the creation of parallel worlds in any short-term performance of experiments where no statistical inference could be made of the outcomes. More precisely, the common understanding of the ontology of the MWI as presented in [21, 23–26, 76, 77], even if considered valid, cannot survive for a long period of time with frequent measurements. Hence, as it will be declared in the following, the unstable parallel worlds (histories) that do not confirm the Born rule must be extinct over time.

III. INVESTIGATION: PSEUDO-DETERMINISM AND THE BORN RULE

In this section, based on the viewpoint presented in [75, 76] we will prove our main conclusion about the ontology of the parallel worlds and their unexpected statistical aspects due to the Born rule and quantum probability. The argument is given for the simplest case where the whole quantum measurements which create the parallel worlds are due to performing a single experiment with several possible outcomes for infinitely many times. In fact, we are concerned about a quantum measurement with n possible outcomes $\{|0\rangle, \dots, |n-1\rangle\}$, for $n \geq 2$.²⁰ Hence, we will consider an endless ensemble composed of infinite copies of the quantum state (II.1), and assume that the agent performs infinite measurements with an apparatus that assigns one i to each observed $|i\rangle$.

We have to emphasize that here we have not considered any imposed condition on the quantum state (II.1), including an intrinsic symmetry among the outcome probabilities (i.e., $|\alpha_0|^2 = \dots = |\alpha_{n-1}|^2 = \frac{1}{n}$), or a predictable situation such as $|\alpha_i| = 1$ for a specific i . Therefore, each parallel world ω is encoded with an infinite sequence $S_\omega = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$ composed of elements of $\{0, \dots, n-1\}$, i.e.: The equality of $a_i = k$ means the observation of $|k\rangle$ in the i -th measurement.²¹ Indeed, any of the infinite sequences $S_\omega = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$ can be assumed as a real number in $[0, 1]$ whenever the numbers

²⁰ We note that what is observed as an outcome in a quantum mechanical experiment, especially as is considered in the MWI, is one of the eigenvalues, not of the eigenstates. But for simplicity in the discussions, we use the concepts of eigenvalues and eigenstates interchangeably.

²¹ In principle, before performing the first measurement we have an agent and an endless ensemble of quantum state $|\psi\rangle$. In other words, we simply assume that initially we have only one world and one agent. After the first measurement, according to the MWI, n parallel worlds are created, each represented by a number $a_1 \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. When the created agents perform their second measurements, according to the MWI, we will have n^2 parallel worlds, each specified by a set of two numbers $\{a_1, a_2\}$ with $a_1, a_2 \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. Similarly, after performing k measurements, we have n^k distinct parallel worlds, each specified by a set of k numbers $\{a_1, \dots, a_k\}$ with $a_1, \dots, a_k \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. Hence, as $k \rightarrow \infty$, each sequence $S = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$, with $a_i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, actually represents a specific parallel world.

are considered in base n . In fact, the infinite sequence $S_\omega = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^\infty$ can be rewritten as:

$$s_\omega = 0.a_1a_2a_3\cdots, \quad (\text{III.1})$$

which shows a real number in $[0, 1]$. Let us refer to s_ω as the *code* of the world ω , or simply the *world's code*. Set Ω to be the set of all created parallel worlds in this process. For technical reasons, we will split Ω into two disjoint portions Ω_1 and Ω_2 , where Ω_1 consists of those parallel worlds whose codes terminate with infinite $(n-1)$ s, while $\Omega_2 := \Omega - \Omega_1$. We must emphasize that the set of the world's codes of the elements of Ω_1 , shown by I_1 , is actually the set of all rational numbers in $[0, 1]$ with finite non-zero fractional digits in base n . Therefore, I_1 is countable and has Lebesgue measure zero [31]. Set $s_1 : \Omega_1 \rightarrow I_1$ to be the invertible function of the world's code map which uniquely sends each parallel world $\omega \in \Omega_1$ to its world's code s_ω . Let $\bar{\mu}_1$ be the induced Lebesgue measure on Ω_1 via s_1^{-1} ;

$$\bar{\mu}_1 = s_{1*}^{-1}(\mu), \quad (\text{III.2})$$

wherein μ is the standard Lebesgue measure. Thus, as we emphasized above:

$$\bar{\mu}_1(\Omega_1) = \mu(I_1) = 0. \quad (\text{III.3})$$

The above separation lets us assign a unique parallel world of Ω_2 to each point of $I_2 = [0, 1]$. In fact, the common elements of I_1 and I_2 have exactly two representations as (III.1) in base n , and each representation is the world's code of a distinct parallel world in the ontology of the MWI. This is the main reason for dividing Ω to two disjoining parts Ω_1 and Ω_2 . Strictly speaking, both sides of equality

$$0.a_1\cdots(a_k-1)\overline{(n-1)} = 0.a_1\cdots a_k\bar{0} \quad (\text{III.4})$$

represent the same value in $[0, 1]$ for each $k \geq 1$ and any $a_k \geq 1$, whereas

$$\{a_1, \cdots, a_k - 1, n - 1, n - 1, n - 1, \cdots\} \quad \text{and} \quad \{a_1, \cdots, a_k, 0, 0, 0, \cdots\} \quad (\text{III.5})$$

are the infinite sequences of two different worlds. Hence, transferring the parallel world of the former sequence to Ω_1 leaves a unique parallel world in Ω_2 for each point of I_2 . Thus, after performing the above consideration in defining Ω_1 and Ω_2 , each element of Ω_2 , say ω , would be uniquely encoded with a definite number $s_\omega \in I_2$ in base n . Let $s_2 : \Omega_2 \rightarrow I_2$ be the invertible world's code map that sends each parallel world $\omega \in \Omega_2$ to its world's code $s_\omega \in I_2$, and define $\bar{\mu}_2$ to be the induced Lebesgue measure on Ω_2 via s_2^{-1} , i.e.;

$$\bar{\mu}_2 = s_{2*}^{-1}(\mu). \quad (\text{III.6})$$

Therefore, we obtain:

$$\bar{\mu}_2(\Omega_2) = \mu(I_2) = 1. \quad (\text{III.7})$$

Thus, according to (III.3) and (III.7), for the induced Lebesgue measure

$$\bar{\mu} = \bar{\mu}_1 \oplus \bar{\mu}_2 \quad (\text{III.8})$$

on Ω we read:

$$\bar{\mu}(\Omega) = \bar{\mu}_1(\Omega_1) + \bar{\mu}_2(\Omega_2) = 1. \quad (\text{III.9})$$

Consequently, $\bar{\mu}$ is, in fact, a probability measure on Ω , and hence, the $\bar{\mu}$ -measure of any measurable subset of Ω is meant as the probability of the occurrence of its elements as parallel worlds in the ontology of the MWI.

Now let us examine the validity of the Born rule in the created parallel worlds in Ω . Since in the assumptions of the MWI it is supposed that the experiences of the sentient beings of each parallel world are identical to that of observers in single-world interpretations of quantum mechanics, hence it is theoretically/empirically expected that the Born rule must be approved of in almost all the created parallel worlds by performing the measurement for infinite times. However, it is just an expectation that must be proved or refuted by strict scrutiny. Indeed, the main objective of our study is to figure out the number of parallel worlds whose sentient beings confirm the Born rule empirically. In other words, we are enthusiastic about measuring the size of the set of parallel worlds in Ω whose sentient beings experience the Born rule. Let us denote this subset of Ω with \mathcal{B} , as the abbreviation of the word "Born".

Evaluating the size of \mathcal{B} must be performed by employing the approaches of measure theory via the induced Lebesgue measure $\bar{\mu}$ on Ω introduced in (III.8). On the other hand, we will see that \mathcal{B} is a measurable set and, hence, its measure $\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B})$ is a well-defined concept. However, as specified above, since $\bar{\mu}$ is a probability measure, then $\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B})$ indicates the probability of approving the Born rule among the parallel worlds of Ω . Therefore, by computing $\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B})$ as the probability of occurrence of \mathcal{B} we will answer to the following question:

What is the probability for approving the Born rule (confirming that the probability of observing λ_i is $|\alpha_i|^2$ for each i) among the parallel worlds of Ω ?

More precisely, we are interested in evaluating the possibility of obtaining the correct probability of the outcomes among the parallel worlds by performing infinite measurements. Before further investigations we have to emphasize that the Born rule is refuted in all elements of Ω_1 , that is we will have: $\mathcal{B} \subset \Omega_2$. In fact, since the world's code of each element of Ω_2 terminates with infinite $(n - 1)$ s, then the probability of observing $|n - 1\rangle$ is practically equal to one regardless of the amplitude of $|\alpha_{n-1}|^2$. Thus, if the parallel world ω belongs to \mathcal{B} it must be included in Ω_2 .

On the other hand, for the parallel world $\omega \in \Omega_2$ with the world's code $s_\omega = 0.a_1a_2a_3 \cdots \in I_2$, the probability of observing $|k\rangle$ is a statistical concept given by the eventual density formula:

$$p_k(s_\omega) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{k,a_i}. \quad (\text{III.10})$$

This formula provides the empirical assessment of the Born rule via the frequency interpretation of the probability in the MWI. The next theorem is an ontological scrutiny based on the ergodic theorem [8, 9] that extracts the true valuation of $\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B})$ as the probability of the appearance of the parallel worlds whose sentient beings confirm the Born rule according to the following equation

$$p_k(s_\omega) = |\alpha_k|^2, \quad (\text{III.11})$$

for all k s, wherein $p_k(s_\omega)$ is defined by (III.10). According to the main assumptions of the MWI presented in [75], a reasonable expectation is that almost all parallel worlds would be able to get the

result (III.11) from the experiments but the next theorem shows an unexpected result.

Theorem 2; *In almost all parallel worlds created by a specific quantum measurement with n outcomes, the agents will obtain $p_k = \frac{1}{n}$ from the eventual density formula (III.10) for any k , regardless of the structure of the quantum state $|\psi\rangle = \alpha_0|0\rangle + \dots + \alpha_{n-1}|n-1\rangle$. In other words, if there is no total symmetry for the possible outcomes (i.e. there exists some i with $|\alpha_i|^2 \neq \frac{1}{n}$), then the sentient beings of a parallel world have actually no practical chance of approving the Born rule by obtaining the correct results $p_k = |\alpha_k|^2$ for all k s. More precisely, the probability of approving the Born rule $\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B})$ among the created parallel worlds is zero for a general quantum state $|\psi\rangle$.*

Proof; To prove the theorem one has to calculate $\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B})$ with strict methods of the ergodic theory provided \mathcal{B} is measurable. Let us assume that \mathcal{B} is measurable. Then, as mentioned above we have:

$$\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B}) = \bar{\mu}_2(\mathcal{B}) = \mu(s_2(\mathcal{B})), \quad (\text{III.12})$$

which the right-hand side term is the Lebesgue measure of the set of real numbers in I_2 whose digits satisfy the equation (III.11). Here, we will show that for the general quantum state (II.1) with no definite symmetry among the outcomes, we will obtain $\mu(s_2(\mathcal{B})) = 0$. This means that \mathcal{B} is a null set and, hence, measurable. To see this, it must be proven that for almost all real numbers $s_\omega \in I_2$ the probability amplitudes $p_k(s_\omega)$ will not fulfill the equality of (III.11). Now, let $T : I_2 \rightarrow I_2$ be the well-known ergodic map $x \mapsto nx \pmod{1}$. We also consider $f_k : I_2 \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as the indicator function of $[\frac{k}{n}, \frac{k+1}{n})$:

$$f_k(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \in [\frac{k}{n}, \frac{k+1}{n}) \\ 0, & x \notin [\frac{k}{n}, \frac{k+1}{n}) \end{cases}, \quad (\text{III.13})$$

for an arbitrary $0 \leq k \leq n-1$. Then, the Birkhoff's theorem [8] asserts that for all k and almost all $s_\omega \in I_2$ we will obtain:²²

$$p_k(s_\omega) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} f_k(T^i(s_\omega)) = \int_I f_k d\mu = \frac{1}{n}, \quad (\text{III.14})$$

wherein T^i is the iterated composition of T with itself for i times: $T^i(x) = n^i x \pmod{1}$. In fact, the first equality in (III.14) comes from statistical equation (III.10), since $f_k(T^i(s_\omega)) = \delta_{k, a_{i+1}}$ for $s_\omega = 0.a_1 a_2 a_3 \dots$. Moreover, the second equation in (III.14) is the main assertion of Birkhoff's theorem [8, 9].²³ Therefore, if $J \subset I_2$ is the set of real numbers that satisfy (III.14), then $\mathcal{B} \subset \Omega_2 - s_2^{-1}(J)$ is a null set and, hence measurable. Consequently, $\bar{\mu}(\mathcal{B})$, the probability of the appearance of \mathcal{B} , is a well-defined concept and equals zero. This finishes the theorem. **Q.E.D.**

As it is clear from the measure-theoretic proof of **Theorem 2**, although the probability of approving the Born rule is zero for the general quantum state (II.1), there exist, howsoever rarely, parallel worlds

²² This conclusion is, in fact, equivalent to a well-known fact in the literature of ergodic theory that states almost all real numbers are *simply normal* in base n .

²³ See [16] for a nice presentation of the theorem.

whose sentient beings confirm the rule empirically. The present parallel world which is practically identical to the physical world assumed in single-world interpretations of quantum mechanics such as the Copenhagen interpretation, is in fact one of these rare cases. Strictly speaking, although it is a null set, \mathcal{B} is not empty. In particular, based on the Eggleston theorem [7] \mathcal{B} has a positive Hausdorff dimension and hence, comprises uncountable parallel worlds. Anyway, the rarity of the historical experiences of the present parallel world in the ontology of the MWI is one of the interesting results of **Theorem 2**. In fact, as we will discuss in the following **Theorem 2** leads to some more peculiar and profound understandings of the ontological aspects of the MWI and also of the fundamental features of the statistical behaviors of quantum mechanical experiments.

In principle, **Theorem 2** asserts that for a general experiment in quantum mechanics, the practical probability of the confirmation of the Born rule is zero among all possible histories of observations. In other words, the confirmation of the Born rule is only accidentally possible for the special case of symmetric outcomes $|\alpha_0|^2 = \dots = |\alpha_{n-1}|^2 = \frac{1}{n}$. Strictly speaking, when there is a total symmetry for all outcomes the ergodic theorem result incidentally aligns with the prediction of the Born rule. Thus, whenever the existence measures of outcomes are not equally weighted the result is quite disappointing and except in a null set of parallel worlds, the physical experiences in all parallel worlds are in contrast to the experiences in the physical universe of any single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics. In practice, this conclusion does not agree with the common understanding of the MWI as presented in the literature [76, 77].

More precisely, if for some k we have $|\alpha_k|^2 \neq \frac{1}{n}$, then the probability of finding a parallel world in Ω whose sentient beings obtain (III.11) empirically is zero and, hence, the extensive confirmation of the Born rule in everyday physics and observed natural events such as the blue color of the sky and the reddish of the sun at sunset, together with its significant role in quantum statistical mechanics and quantum thermodynamics seriously undermines the MWI of quantum mechanics. In other words, based on the assertion of **Theorem 2**, if the MWI is an authentic theory, then the probability of observing the blue color of the sky and the reddish sun at sunset, the natural phenomena which are strongly acknowledged as the immediate consequences of the Born rule [77], is statistically zero. Therefore, based on the above argumentation, it seems that **Theorem 2** provides one of the most powerful criticisms against the MWI.

In addition, as we mentioned above, assuming a total symmetry for outcomes to approve the Born rule in the MWI is, in fact, a reduction of the probability rule to the special case which the assertion of **Theorem 2** accidentally aligns with. More precisely, as we have just shown in proving **Theorem 2**, it seems that deriving the Born rule via the symmetry argument in statistical mechanisms merely stems from the background symmetry which settles in the core of Birkhoff's ergodic theorem, and has nothing to do with the frequency interpretation of quantum probability. Therefore, although the Born-Vaidman rule is confirmed by **Theorem 2** in the statistical picture of the MWI, its validity stems from some structural facts outside of quantum mechanics and the interpretation. Considering the symmetry assumption for proving the Born rule in the MWI is, in fact, a controversial topic with numerous objections,²⁴ and **Theorem 2** shows the unreliability of the proof in the statistical version by disclosing the irrelevant but inevitable role of total symmetry in the argument.

²⁴ See for example [6, 17, 33, 44, 52, 60, 63, 66].

The assertion of **Theorem 2** is essentially true regardless of what interpretation we use for quantum mechanics provided each parallel world is considered as a possible history/statistics of the observations. Thus, based on the astonishing conclusion of **Theorem 2**, the statistics of the observations that approve the Born rule have to pass an extremely special history of measurements. Hence, the empirical confirmation of the Born rule in quantum mechanical experiments suggests that there must exist some kind of fine-tuning process for the history/statistics of quantum observations. Such an understanding of quantum mechanics provides a somewhat pseudo-deterministic picture of the theory so that the overall history of previous observations may affect the outcomes of the next measurements. This profound prospect toward the fundamental mechanism of quantum mechanics is an inevitable consequence of the Born rule and its statistical nature, regardless of accepting or refuting the MWI.

Anyway, such a pseudo-deterministic picture is in fundamental disagreement with the unlimited ontology of the MWI as expressed in [21, 23, 24]. However, based on **Corollary 1** this pseudo-deterministic picture of quantum mechanics must be extended thoroughly to the ontological structure of the MWI. All in all, from the contents of **Theorem 1** and **Theorem 2** we conclude that:

Corollary 2; *The unconstrained ontology of the MWI must be confined to a null set through any long-term process of observations. In other words, the ontology of the MWI must be seriously modified based on the pseudo-deterministic statistical picture of quantum mechanics discovered in **Theorem 2**.*

Anyway, the contraction from Ω to \mathcal{B} , as demonstrated in **Corollary 2**, although has not been acknowledged manifestly in Everett's theory [23–25], is an inevitable statistical picture of the long-term ontology of the MWI.²⁵ However, it seems that the consequences of this contraction have always been considered in the ontological aspects of the MWI, since, as it is declared in [21, 26, 76, 77], it is strongly believed that the experiences of sentient beings living in each parallel world are identical to those of the agents who live in a physical universe of a single-world interpretation of quantum mechanics. **Theorem 2** shows that if one considers only the Born rule as a statistically experienced law the above claim could be true just for the parallel worlds that belong to \mathcal{B} .²⁶ Therefore, as mentioned above, although not explicitly described elsewhere, the MWI ontology restriction from Ω to \mathcal{B} , has implicitly been incorporated in the core of the explanations of the interpretation without any rigorous theoretical argumentation similar to the arguments of **Theorem 2** and **Corollary 2**.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we studied the role of the Born rule in the MWI via the frequency interpretation of probability. In the first step, we showed in **Theorem 1** that the statistical interpretation of the Born rule can be derived from the other principles of quantum mechanics regardless of accepting or refuting the wave function collapse postulate. Hence, we argued that the Born rule must be imposed on the unconstrained ontology of the MWI in the statistical picture of the interpretation.

²⁵ However, as we specified above, this restriction of ontology is indispensable for long-term observations and has nothing to do with short-term experiments with no statistical information.

²⁶ Moreover, if we insist on other statistical principles of quantum mechanics such as Heisenberg's uncertainty principle we have to confine the MWI ontology one more time to a proper subset of \mathcal{B} .

Next, by employing Birkhoff's ergodic theorem we showed in **Theorem 2** that approving the Born rule among the created parallel worlds is, in fact, impossible, except for some extremely special worlds. Therefore, **Theorem 2** could be assumed as a powerful criticism of the MWI since its assertion is empirically in contrast to the vast amount of laboratory confirmations and extensive natural observations confirming the rule. Strictly speaking, based on **Theorem 2**, it is extremely improbable to live in a parallel world that statistically embraces the Born rule.

Thereafter, we explained that the rarity of the parallel worlds whose sentient beings confirm the Born rule could be considered as a pseudo-deterministic picture of quantum mechanics in statistical aspects of the theory. More precisely, it was shown that the Born rule provides a pseudo-deterministic law among all the possible histories of quantum mechanical measurements to follow only the special possibilities that align with the Born rule statistically. This shrinks the ontology of the MWI to an extremely constrained theory. However, such a peculiar picture of the MWI ontology disclosed by rigorous measure-theoretic methods has not ever been reported manifestly in the literature.

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